

Coherence and telicity in adults' event representations

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Abstract: Events are effortlessly segmented out of streaming reality. We can refer to them with verbs, along with aspectual morphemes and adverbs to focalize on specific parts. This suggests that, besides visual clues or statistical structures, also primitives facilitating event individuation may exist. Here we focus on the notion of endpoint arising from telicity, and on how (if) their description varies as a function of participants' native language. Participants saw videos showing actions consisting of an activity and an endpoint, combined in their components such that their connectedness could vary. We explored perceptions of these events and their descriptions in four different languages. Participants considered all events as coherent regardless of the inconsistencies between the action performed and the endpoint for the event. Verb selection in describing the events was influenced by the nature of the events, modulating the choice of result vs. manner verbs, but not by participants' natural language. These findings highlight the role of teleological information in the process of event individuation, suggesting that manner and goals are fundamental properties of how the mind conceive the events, over and above their linguistic realizations.

1 Introduction

As Davidson (1980) acknowledged, while events do not require objects to exist, they do seem to be mostly about changes in objects. As concrete entities, objects can be created, changed or modified, and enter into dynamic relations captured in the form of events. Much is known about objects and their representation. At 2 months of age the object concept is already in place. By their first year, infants can represent objects, assign them a spatio-temporal location, conceive of them as being permanent even when out of sight, use spatio-temporal discontinuousness as evidence for their numerical identity, categorize them by means of some basic properties, and represent them multi-modally (Carey, 2009).

If events without objects are (almost) empty, objects without events are (almost) blind. In spite of their abstract and ephemeral nature, events play an essential role in language and the mind. There is no experience of the world, or of ourselves, without the temporal dimension of a passing event. Yet our knowledge about object representation stands in stark contrast with how little is known about event representations, how and when we can reason about them and what their basic conceptual components are. If we have objects in our ontologies, it only seems logical that events also partake in them. Indeed, the purpose events could serve in our minds is to help put together objects, properties, and relations, in order to make sense of an ever changing reality. While providing a definition of events proves difficult (Casati & Varzi, 2020; Pianesi & Varzi, 2000), Davidson (1980) emphasized that we can count on them having locations, taking time, being embedded in causal relationships, and, as mentioned, involving changes in a substance or object. Events, *qua* artifacts of our mind, behave as items of information, or in Davidson's words, as particulars, which we may quantify over and refer to, describe and redescribe, and identify with either physical, mental, or physiological happenings.

That events have a fundamental role in human cognition is suggested by several lines of research. Adults process the flow of activity consisting of actions, objects, and the spatio-temporal context into these meaningful units that inform their understanding of the happenings around them (Levine, Buchsbaum, Hirsh-Pasek, & Golinkoff, 2019). Event boundaries, whether beginnings or ends, arise spontaneously as the current activity deviates from its expected course, such as when there are relevant changes in the motion

of entities, the spatio-temporal context, or actors' goals. For example, in an event of *running*, the beginning of the running motion is taken as the initial event boundary and the ending of such motion as the final event boundary, thus delimiting the contours of the event. This happens as the perceived changes induce a comparison between the previous and subsequent relevant properties, which ultimately helps determine the segmentation of the events (Baker & Levin, 2015; Levine, Buchsbaum, Hirsh-Pasek, & Golinkoff, 2019; Richmond & Zacks, 2017).

In addition, information about the goals and intentions of actors has been argued to be relevant to event individuation for both adults and infants (Baldwin & Baird, 2001; Heider & Simmel, 1944; Southgate & Csibra, 2009; Southgate, Johnson, & Csibra, 2008). For example, infants as young as 13 months of age can already infer the goal of an action before it is actually completed by hypothesizing its end state on the basis of a principle of efficiency that justifies the actions of agents (Southgate & Csibra, 2009), even when an action is biomechanically impossible (Southgate, Johnson, & Csibra, 2008) or the agent's actions are unsuccessful (Meltzoff, 1995), and even well before infants can themselves conduct reaching actions (Liu, Brooks, & Spelke, 2019). In sum, this evidence seems to indicate that adults and infants are conceptually equipped to tell apart the basic components of events, namely, path, manner, goal, actor, or object, out of the on stream reality, allowing them to rapidly draw inferences about their internal structure (Strickland & Keil, 2011).

The particular way in which the grammar allows us to characterize, describe, or individuate events, that is, via the specific lexical aspectual classes, may guide us to understand their structure and their role in our mental life. Theories of lexical aspect suggest that events may occur in a particular way, and may have an inherent *telos*, or an endpoint: thus, if there is an event of *running*, we may think of it as atelic, with no predefined ending point, or as having one, such as *to the finish line*, a bounded path phrase. In this latter case it would not be an *activity* but an *accomplishment*. Similarly, an event of *eating* may be described as atelic, without a predetermined ending point, or as telic if we decide that we should measure it up by using as reference the progress of the action on an object such as *an apple*. This reference provides the scale relative to which the event's degree of change is ordered (Depraetere, 1995; Filip, 2008; Krifka, 2019). Choosing to focus on the telic or atelic nature of an event serves the purpose of

individuating a particular happening, as it might be relevant to classifying it, remembering it, or communicating it.

These considerations suggest that language via telicity, in particular, has a crucial role in event representation, as it can be an individuation tool to select among the available interpretations of events (Wagner & Carey, 2003), thus playing an adjuvant role during identification tasks, in contrast to atelicity (Ji & Papafragou, 2020). At the same time, telicity is present in sign languages and pseudosigns (Strickland et al., 2015), showing its modality-independent nature. It can also affect, rather than being affected by, the online processing of sentences (Malaia, Wilbur, & Weber-Fox, 2009; Misersky, Slivac, Hagoort, & Flecken, 2021), and is associated to a characteristic pattern of brain activation during verb encoding tasks (Romagno, Rota, Ricciardi, & Pietrini, 2012). These considerations rather support a mediating role for telicity in event cognition, over and above its role in language.

The focus of the current research is to explore the double-faced nature of telicity, as the starting point to investigate the mental representation of events, and the potential role of linguistic encoding in this representation. For that purpose, we prepared a set of scenes in which we showed silent motion events. The choice of motion events is not innocent. Such events are defined by two important parameters: path and manner of motion. By 10-12 months of age, before language production is established, humans are already sensitive to them (Song, Pruden, Golinkoff, & Hirsh-Pasek, 2016; Pruden, Hirsh-Pasek, Maguire, & Meyer, 2004). At 18 months, when language production has started, toddlers can already associate verb labels to actions, whose invariant features (that is, manner and path) help make them stand out, and extend those labels to other instances of that category (Maguire et al., 2002). Indeed, languages instantiate different lexicalization patterns for manner and path (Talmy, 2000). Thus, the conceptualization of motion events must be grounded on preverbal cognitive abilities. For these reasons, motion events are ideal to study the influence of language on event conceptualization. Our strategy will be to present participants events deprived of language, representing a well completed action or an action in which the proper ending has been modified. With them, we will study how a proper telic structure influences event perception and participants' description. In particular, we will focus on how language influences, if it does, such descriptions.

In our scenes, the endpoint or telos was determined either by a bounded path of motion (a motion event with predefined starting and endpoints, in the case of events of change of

location), or by a change of property (such as ending up being inflated or deflated, in the case of change of state events), which can also be conceived as a bounded path leading to the attainment of a property. We will refer to both these instances of bounded path as *result*. In the linguistics literature, change of location and change of state events have been shown to share important similarities in their underlying argument structure and aspectual properties (Hale & Keyser, 2002; Mateu, 2002); thus, we place our focus specifically on bounded paths as they positively contribute to the telicity of both change of location and change of state events.

Our language sample included English, Italian, Japanese, and Spanish. These were chosen to encompass the main patterns afforded by language to encode telicity via result information, and to also instantiate the well-known continuum between verb- and satellite-framedness (Talmy, 2000). Specifically, these languages differ in terms of their capability to encode result meaning via a phrasal component providing the ordering scale that measures up the event and determines its endpoint (Mateu & Acedo-Matellán, 2012; Washio, 1997, Table 1). Verb-framed languages such as Italian and Spanish differ from English in that the former allow the creation of resultative structures only by means of verbs encoding the notion of change or path by themselves, which may appear along with an additional phrasal element further specifying the properties of the resulting state or endpoint (e.g., *drive crazy*, *fly to Barcelona*). On the other pole of the continuum, satellite-framed languages such as English can express result not only via simple resultative structures but also by means of weak and strong resultative structures, both containing an atelic verb and a phrasal element that specifies the endpoint of the event or resulting property (e.g., *hammer the metal flat*, *run her shoes ragged*), and which only differ in terms of the verb's transitivity or intransitivity. By contrast, Japanese offers a midway approach between the poles instantiated by verb and satellite-framed languages (Croft, Barðdal, Hollmann, Sotirova, & Taoka, 2010). In Japanese, both the simple resultative strategy and the weak resultative strategy with atelic transitive verbs are available to express events with a result state. Yet, at the same time, Japanese disallows weak resultatives with atelic intransitive verbs and strong resultatives. The existence of differences in the complexity of the possible result structures in these languages can serve as a test case on how language influences event perception. If language is constitutive of event perception (Papafragou, Massey, & Gleitman, 2006; Pulverman, Golinkoff, Hirsh-Pasek, & Buresh, 2008), then we expect participants' responses to reflect language-specific patterns in the way the notion of result is perceived, reported, and

affected by the disruption of the events' telic structures brought about by their manipulation. If, instead, language differences remain at the surface of participants' perception and conception of events, then we should only expect a minor role for it, whereas the nature and structure of events themselves should drive the bulk of potential effects on participants' responses.

Table 1. Resultative constructions

	Italian / Spanish	Japanese	English
Simple resultative (<i>drive crazy / fly to Barcelona</i>)	Yes	Yes	Yes
Weak resultative (<i>wipe the table clean / hammer the metal flat</i>)	No	Yes / No	Yes
Strong resultative (<i>run her shoes ragged</i>)	No	No	Yes

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Method

2.1.1 Participants

Seventy-nine participants took part to the study. Of them, 21 were English native speakers ($M_{age}=43.9$, 9 women), 21 were Spanish native speakers ($M_{age}=32.23$, 7 women), 21 were Italian native speakers ($M_{age}=29.8$, 8 women), and 16 were Japanese native speakers ($M_{age}=32.75$, 12 women). The participants were recruited via *Amazon Turk* and received \$10-\$12 as compensation for their participation.

2.1.2 Stimuli

The stimuli consisted of a set of movies depicting events, which can be broadly categorized as actions performed on objects. The acting entity was a hand, which performed actions that caused different types of movement or changes on an object. This was done without any contact between the hand and the object. Indeed, to ensure that the perception of events could not be reduced to previous perceptual experiences, the scenes always contained an element of violation of physical laws. For example, an event

of pushing was realized without physical contact between the object and the actor causing the displacement. The events were categorized into two broad categories: *change of location* events and *change of state* events. Both classes of events are characterized by their telicity, which is provided by the existence of an ending point in the path of motion of the object or a change in the properties of the object, respectively.

Some of the events that were represented in the stimuli could be described using a composite of a semelfactive verb in its atelic reading, that is, interpreted as a succession of minimal events such as *knocking*, and hence equivalent to an activity event, and a path of motion or change of property providing the endpoint of the event. This combination gave as a result events that could be classified as telic. Alternatively, the events could also be described using inherently telic verb descriptors.

The events were crossed with a second parameter, which for brevity we will call *Coherent* and *Incoherent*. The event structure of the Coherent movies was fully preserved. To create the Incoherent movies, we digitally modified the Coherent events in such a way that their endings, or their full structure, would also be incoherent from the point of view of the event structure. This was realized by inverting the action sequence of Coherent movies, or by adding an incoherent ending to the sequence. By using the word 'incoherent' we do not refer to a logical violation, or (to a lesser extent) a strictly physical violation; in a sense, all the events we test violate physical principles. Rather, our incoherent events are meant to test the effect of deviations from the normal course of action and the expected causal chains generating an end state. Thus, in the case of Incoherent flattening events, a foam ball's size increased with each downward movement of the hand(s) supposed to flatten it, or in the case of Incoherent gathering events, a set of toy blocks was scattered away as the actor performed an (inward) gathering movement. This manipulation was meant to test the extent to which deviations from the connectedness of events, and possibly the compliance to physical laws, obtained by disrupting the correct causal relations between actions and results, would lead participants to shift their focus from one event parameter to another and report it changing the balance of verbs encoding *the way in which* the event occurred and those encoding how it ended.

A total of 20 movies (with an average duration of 5.7s) were generated. Objects' affordances and the feasibility of suitable manual actions determined the number of possible events, which were classified in accordance with the type of action. Change of location events included equivalent pairs of actions: (a) shoving, punching, and (b)

gathering, scattering; totaling 8 movies, as each action type had a coherent and incoherent version. In the same manner, change of state events were instantiated by equivalent pairs of actions: (c) clenching, knocking, (d) pressing, squashing, and (e) unflattening, scratching; producing as a result 12 movies, with coherent and incoherent versions for each action type. The pairs of actions were split into two lists to which participants were randomly assigned (see Table S1 in Supplemental Materials; Figures 2 and 3 for examples; stimuli available at <https://osf.io/fq238/>). In addition, a control movie was included in each list to verify that participants could tell apart incoherences (due to mismatches between the sequentiality of the agent's actions and the effects on the object) and altogether impossible actions. The control movie showed a hand performing a twisting action and a tower block moving forward, two completely unconnected situations. The stimuli were recorded using a Panasonic AG UX 180, with the Green Screen recording technique. To generate the actions without contact, an actor acted onto the objects at a distance as if she were touching them, and a second actor dressed in green would move them in synchrony. Movies were then edited with *Final Cut Pro* (at 50 fps, 1920 × 1080 pixels, QuickTime movie) to adjust the synchronization and visual parameters.

Figure 1. Three different types of objects were used: 15 pieces of toy blocks, a pink foam ball, and a tower of stacked toy blocks.

After editing, the movies showed a green background and a grey flat surface, on which an object stood. No sound accompanied the movies. Three different types of objects were used: a pink foam ball, a tower of stacked toy blocks, and 15 pieces of toy blocks (see Figure 1). The actress wore black clothing and appeared on the background of the scene. A hand or two hands performed a variety of actions, which can be broadly characterized

as *flattening*, *pushing*, *reshaping*, *twisting*, *scattering*, and *gathering*. If objects were being pushed, they moved either from left to right or center, or conversely from right to left or center. For Coherent events, objects moved according to the direction of the force exerted by the hand, i.e., a downward force caused the foam fall to flatten, whereas an upward directed force caused the foam ball to unflatten or reshape (see Figure 2). For Incoherent events, objects behaved in ways contrary to the direction of the exerted force, i.e., if a fist pushed forward a tower of stacked toy blocks, the latter moved backward against the direction of the force exerted by the fist (see Figure 3).

Figure 2. In Coherent events, objects moved according to the direction of the force exerted by the hand, i.e., a downward force caused the foam fall to flatten and a pushing fist caused the block to move forward.

Figure 3. In Incoherent events, objects behaved in ways contrary to the direction of the exerted force, i.e., an upward force caused the foam fall to flatten, and if a fist pushed forward the tower of stacked toy blocks, it then moved backward against the direction of the force exerted by the fist.

A questionnaire containing a set of questions and a list of verbs from which participants had to choose the best match for the actions seen was prepared in Google Forms, translated into the relevant languages by expert native speakers with experience in language studies and translation (see Figure S4 in Supplemental Materials). Stimuli and data are available at

2.1.3 Procedure

Participants were asked to watch 11 videos for an allotted time of 50 minutes. They were told that the movies had been digitally modified but that sometimes the procedure resulted in error. To elicit coherence judgments, they were asked to help the Production Editor (PE) identify the movies wrongly composed, by providing details and descriptions of them. They were explicitly asked to obviate the fact that there was no contact between the hand and the object during the experiment. Participants were told their task consisted in helping the PE, who was already aware of the absence of contact between the agent's hand and the object(s), by providing as many details as necessary for him/her to imagine the content of the videos. Questions were aimed at understanding how participants segmented the videos into events, how they were affected by disruptions in the connectedness of the movies, and how their language affected their descriptions of events, especially in relation to their tendency to focus on manner and result (i.e. a bounded path contributing to the telicity of the event) in them. For our purposes, of particular relevance, participants were asked to choose a set of manner or result verbs out of a ready-made list of bare verbs coding manner and result, to describe the event shown in the movie, so as to gather information about the saliency of these parameters in the events they saw. They were further asked to freely describe the events and, finally, to indicate whether there were any noticeable errors in the composition of the movies. This question was meant to capture participants' feelings about the correctness of the sequence, as a way to probe whether the distinction between coherent and incoherent sequences, as we realized it, corresponded to their perception of correctness. In answering the last question, participants were asked to obviate aesthetic defects in the composition of the movies such as glitches or blotchy patches. In its stead, participants were expected to come up with problems of coherence in the events depicted in the videos. We had previously run a pilot test to determine the suitability of the questions.

Four different versions of the questionnaire were prepared, one per each language tested (Japanese, Italian, Spanish, and English), resulting from the best translation of the content (see Table S2 in Supplemental Materials). The two lists of stimuli were counterbalanced between participants.

The experiment was run online on *Amazon Turk* and *Google Forms*. The material collected was analyzed offline. A Japanese expert translator translated the responses into Spanish and English to complement the languages mastered by the authors, and directly informed of the meanings of the expressions when needed.

2.2 Results

Participants' answers were analyzed and classified as appropriate depending on the nature of the question (see *Supplemental Materials*). We are interested at how disruption of the connectedness of an event affects its perception, toggling participants' focus on different dimensions they may have been using in encoding the event. Specifically, we tracked participants' explicit perception of consistency of the events, as well as changes in the choices of language descriptors in reporting the content of the events.

For the first question, we analyzed participants' judgments of which movies had been composed with errors, as explicitly indicated by their direct answers. We call this value *movie coherence judgment*.

For the second question, we computed two indicators meant to capture implicit differences in the coherence of the movies and the relative importance of manner and result parameters in their conceptualizations. To do this, we analyzed two responses related to the verbs participants chose to describe the events. First, we asked a group of expert linguists who had not seen the scenes ($n=17$; from postdocs to full professors) to make a binary classification of the verbs selected by the participants, indicating whether they thought the verbs tended to express more manner or more result (bounded path) information. This is a forced classification because, as discussed, the information conveyed by verbal phrases is a function of the grammatical system of each language, as well as the phrase structures in which the verbs are embedded. Nevertheless, our aim was to capture the core of the information a single verb would convey, as our participants saw it, with the aim of identifying potential event parameters as conveyed by language encoding (for discussion see (McNally & Spalek, in press)). With these forced choices, we selected all verbs which at least the 60% of our informants categorized consistently ($n=16$) and discarded those where we found no agreement ($n=2$). Once the main nature of the verbs in the list was determined, we counted how many verbal descriptors from the proposed multiple choice list participants indicated as appropriate to describe the movie, and created an indicator capturing the relative preference to use result verbs as opposed

to manner verbs in participants' choices, which we call *result verb preference* indicator. This was calculated as the ratio between the number of result verb descriptors each participant selected, minus the number of manner verb descriptors, divided by the sum of result verb descriptors plus manner verb descriptors, thus ranging from -1 (preference for manner) to +1 (preference for result). Then, we tried to capture how many (adverbial or prepositional) complements indicating path information they used in their free descriptions of the events. We computed an index analog to that used in the analysis of participants' verb selection, but defined over their spontaneous free descriptions. We first coded the presence or absence of manner, result (bounded path), and unbounded path information in participants' free descriptions. We then computed the ratio between the number of result descriptors minus the number of manner descriptors, divided by the total sums of result descriptors and manner descriptors (hereafter, *free description result preference* indicator). We discuss the three dependent variables below.

First we checked the potential effect of factors not relevant to our investigation. Separate Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney tests with, respectively, Gender and List of stimuli as the independent variables revealed that these factors had no effect on any of the three variables of interest (respectively, movie coherence judgments: $p=0.386$ and $p=0.438$; result verb preference: $p=0.686$ and $p=0.224$; free description result preference: $p=1$ and $p=1$; all values FDR Corrected). We thus disregarded them in successive analyses and focused on the three variables of interest.

Movie coherence judgments. For each participant, we analyzed the average coherence judgment for coherent and incoherent movies, respectively. Overall, participants detected few errors in the movie composition, resulting in high average coherence judgments. Participants rated as highly coherent both coherent and incoherent event movies; indeed, Wilcoxon tests against chance revealed that each and every movie was given coherent judgments at a higher than chance level. To analyze the results, we conducted further non-parametric tests, due to the highly non-normal distribution of the responses.

We then turned to the analysis of the perception of coherence and its relation with native language. Given the experimental design and the non-normality of the data, we computed an Aligned Rank Transform ANOVA (Wobbrock, Findlater, Gergle, & Higgins, 2011) with the aligned ranks of coherence judgment as the dependent variable, Language as a between-participant factor, Coherence as a within-participant factor, and participants as random factor, using the R package ARTool (Kay & Wobbrock, 2020). The analysis

revealed an effect of Coherence ($F(1,75)=18.4$, $p \leq 0.00053$), no effect of language ($p=0.63$) and no interaction ($p=0.70$). While being generally high, participants nevertheless gave higher coherence judgments to coherent ($M=0.99$, $sd=0.0225$) than incoherent movies ($M=0.91$ $sd=0.228$) (see Figure 4).

Verb selections for event description. Next, we turned to participants' verbal reports of the events. We studied how their lexical choices in event characterization was affected by the disruption in their connectedness brought about by an improper ending, as well as the effect of native languages in such choices. As the data were not normally distributed, we computed a second Aligned Rank Transform ANOVA, with result verb preference as the dependent variable, Language as a between-participant factor, Event Coherence as a within-participant factor, and participants as a random factor. The analysis revealed an effect of Coherence ($F(1,75)=44$, $p \leq 5e09$), a weak effect of language ($F(3,75)=2.8$; $p \leq 0.04$), and no interactions ($p=0.44$). There was a general tendency to prefer verbs expressing results, but participants selected more result verbs for *incoherent* ($M=0.628$, $sd=0.3$) than coherent movies ($M=0.432$ $sd=0.28$). Post-hoc analyses of the Language effect run with the R package *emmeans* showed that overall Japanese participants tended to select less result verbs than Italian ($p=0.079$) and Spanish ($p=0.057$) participants (see Figure 4). No other contrast was close to significance.

Manner and result descriptors used in free event description. Finally, we computed a model identical to that defined for the result verb preference, but with the *free description result preference indicator* as the dependent variable. No effect or interaction was found.

2.3

Figure 4. Coherence judgments for Coherent and Incoherent movies by language (1 = Coherent, 0 = Incoherent); Preference for Result Verbs for Coherent and Incoherent movies by language (1 = Result, -1 = Manner).

Discussion

Participants in our language sample including Japanese, Italian, Spanish, and English considered all movies as coherent events regardless of the incoherences purposely introduced in some of the stimuli. It seems that the availability of a plausible teleological schema helped participants individuate events and provide a linguistic description for them. The conceptualization of events did not seem to be affected by language, suggesting that the representation of the scenes took place at a level relatively independent of linguistic encoding. Overall, participants tended to show a preference to include result information for both coherent and incoherent events. Still, this tendency was stronger for incoherent events. These results show that, when facing novel scenes representing events with a disrupted or a correct endpoint, participants perceive their overall structure. Regardless of their native language, they choose descriptors as a function of this structure. This suggests that properties such as manner and result are intrinsically tied to the events, rather than their linguistic descriptions. At the same time, the disruption of the event endpoint, as we realized it, increased the tendency to use verbs encoding result information. This counterintuitive finding can be one of the

manifestations of the importance of goals in human cognition, a characteristic of human nature appearing as early as one year (Csibra, Gergely, Bíró, Koós, & Brockbank, 1999): when some aspect of an event is not clearly structured, participants may overcompensate by stressing a possible endpoint even when this is not clearly contained in the event. This interpretation requires further studies, where a fuller manipulation of event structure may more markedly modulate participants' lexical choices. Indeed, we remark that whether the hypothesis we advanced is correct or not, the strength of the effect did not percolate into their spontaneous descriptions of the event. At the same time, interestingly, no language difference was found in them either. We discuss the import of these results on the general aims of this research below.

3 General discussion

The world is what it is: the collection of state of affairs that occur at any time point. It does not matter whether such states have been brought about in a certain way, or with a certain purpose. These are concepts that are only relevant for our mental life, for *how* we talk about the world, and for how we conceive events. The importance of events and their structure is manifested in the remarkable amount of information that language provides us with to describe them. In fact, a plethora of linguistic evidence makes manifest the role of events in our mental ontology. They play an essential role in the argument structure of verb phrases, informing how syntax should relate participants to event components (Kratzer, 1996; Marantz, 2013; Pykkänen, 2008; Ramchand, 2008). If *one hammers the metal flat*, strict linguistic dependencies tell us that there is a relation holding between an entity fulfilling the action of *hammering* an object (*the metal*), which as a result acquires the property of being *flat*. This description allows us to individuate an event out of the stream reality by using an inherently atelic verb descriptor (*hammering*) for which a result or endpoint is provided by means of the adjective *flat*, temporally delimiting the event. This fundamental component of events' linguistic descriptions is telicity, or lack thereof, on which we focused here. Yet while these relations are cross-linguistically stable, they may be differently realized in languages' surface structure (Beavers, Levin, & Tham, 2010; Talmy, 2000). In Spanish, the same relation can be expressed via the predicate *aplanar el metal a martillazos*, in which the manner component of the action (*a martillazos*) appears as an adjunct to the verb phrase, whose head (*aplanar*) provides the result component

applying to the object (*el metal*), as does the English adjective *flat*. Correspondingly, in Japanese this relation can be instantiated instead by the verbal compound *tataki-nobasu* ('pound'-'extend') (Croft, Barðdal, Hollmann, Sotirova, & Taoka, 2010). Linguistic descriptions constrain the received event's purview, determining the relations holding between participants and the temporal development of the event. Thus, one could assume that events can only be individuated under particular linguistic descriptions, as there do not seem to be other (external) indicators of their internal structure beyond apparent changes in the course of reality.

Under the view that language is necessary to individuate events, notions such as telicity would simply instantiate a property of linguistic expressions (Rothstein, 2008). Alternatively, telicity may be an independent cognitive component, enabling event individuation in humans prior to language. This property of events would not only belong to the linguistic realm but it would also be detectable to viewers witnessing an event with a telos, rather than some notion of completion arising when a particular action finalizes regardless of its inherent ending point (Ji & Papafragou, 2020).

Here we tested whether the existence of an inherent endpoint in the development of events would drive participants' perception of coherence, as our stimuli depicted coherent and incoherent events. In particular we explored telicity arising from reaching the ending point of a path (both location and property related), which in our stimuli was arbitrarily determined by the actor's last hand movement. We designed a set of stimuli depicting events involving an actor and an object, over which an action was performed. In addition to the action component, the events were also composed of a result. The former was performed by the actor applying a force to the object (although never directly), while the latter issued from the force exerted by the actor, which helped delimit the path of motion, or by the inherent properties of the object and the action applied to it. The events could be lexically instantiated by verbs ambiguous between an activity and a semelfactive reading (*push, knock, etc.*), or by others denoting inherently telic events (*flatten, squash, etc.*), which in themselves contain a result state for the event. To understand the role of language in the conceptualization of these events, we explored how participants with different mother tongues selected descriptors for and described the events.

The first conclusion of our study is that participants, irrespective of the language, were willing to consider all movies, both coherent and incoherent, as properly structured events provided that the teleological schema of the action was plausible regardless of any

inconsistencies arising from the combination of unrelated actions and results (Southgate et al., 2008; Southgate & Csibra, 2009). That is, the very possibility to attribute a goal to the agent helped participants delimit the events' boundaries and, consequently, conceptualize them as coherent events. In general, the clues of telicity found in the movies, which could enable the identification of the beginning and endpoints of the events on the basis of their internal properties, and their disruption, did not affect participants' judgements of coherence. Nevertheless, our second result is that participants did refer to the telic nature of the events in their verb choices. Overall, they showed a preference to describe both coherent and incoherent events by means of result verbs. This tendency was comparatively stronger for incoherent events. This suggests that aspectual information was available, but remained a secondary source of information to segment the sequences of actions into events. The availability of aspectual information during event segmentation for coherent events was expected, as no disruption between the action and result sequences had been introduced, making viable the mapping between the temporal structure of the event (its running time) and the scalar structure (instantiated by either changes in the object's position with respect to its path or by some degree of change in the object's size) (Jackendoff, 1996). But, in spite of the mismatching action and result components, participants fulfilled the mapping between the temporal and scalar structure even for incoherent events. This suggests that the processing of the path information available in our events was prioritized over event coherence. That is, the existence of spatiotemporal continuity between the actor's actions and the object's path in the movies facilitated the segmentation of the sequences into events in spite of the coherence violations purposely introduced. These were tolerated without impairing participants' ability to perceive the situation as a whole event. These results highlight the importance of spatiotemporal continuity for events and their segmentation (Zacks & Swallow, 2007; Kominsky, Baker, Keil, & Strickland, 2021).

In no place did we find a hint of a role of language in the conceptualization and description of the events we provided. This indicates that participants' representation of the scenes was constructed at a level relatively independent of linguistic encoding. Thus, our work opens the question of how universal representations of events, which include telicity among other parameters, fit in with the representations generated by their linguistic counterparts. A way to advance in this line of research will be to understand how preverbal infants represent scenes like those we used in the current work, and how, across their linguistic acquisition process, they get to express these events in their first

productions of linguistic descriptions for them. Finally, we want to observe that the current research is a first attempt at studying one of the many aspects that must be tackled with if we want to understand our ability to generate rich descriptions of ephemeral events that from the physical point of view are born and die in a passing moment, but remain engraved, often forever, in our mind. Part of our richness depends on this largely unexplored ability. Unveiling the fundamental blocks that make the richness of our thoughts possible is part and parcel of the explanation of the very nature of the human mind.

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Supplementary files

Supplementary file 1: Supplemental Materials for 'Coherence and telicity in adults' event representations'.

Stimuli and data are available at

https://osf.io/fq238/?view_only=c2e55322c85642078eba3ed043c6c8b4

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Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

Data Availability

Stimuli and data are available at

https://osf.io/fq238/?view_only=c2e55322c85642078eba3ed043c6c8b4